

A tool for outlining scientific past and futures: A case study on Common Bean

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Introduction

Bibliometrics, a term first proposed by Pritchard (1969), consists of applying statistical and mathematical methods to examine the scientific production of a given field, mapping academic communities, networks of researchers and their scientific impact. In this sense, several authors used bibliometric indicators (such as citations, co-citations, keywords) to propose tools and analysis models that evaluate different perspectives of knowledge production. Keathley-Herring (2016) proposed a framework to assess the maturity of a research area. Yang et al. (2020) built a bibliometrics-based research model for studying changes in policy. Zhang (2021) designed a bibliometric framework to chart the evolutionary pathways of scientific innovation. However, just a few papers propose models to map scientific trends, that is, to look at the future of science in a given field. Therefore, in this paper, we propose a framework to identify past, current and future research trends, using the Common Bean (CB) as a case of study. We chose this topic for the reasons outlined below.

Beans are of nutritional, economic, social and cultural importance (Miano et al., 2018; Ferreira & Barrigossi, 2021), as one of the most cultivated and consumed legumes in the world. As a dietary option for low-cost protein intake (Hayat et al. 2014), this food item has particular importance for emerging countries, especially for Brazil, which ranks as the largest grain consumer of the species *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. (Santos et al., 2019), also known as Common Bean (CB) (Chiorato et al. 2018). Considering its obvious implications, the interest in CB naturally extends to the scientific field (Leal, 2019), in which Brazil also stands out for being the only South American country in the top 10 global publications (Bezerra et al., 2022).

In a recent study, Bezerra et al. (2022) outlined the global scientific production related to CB since first publications, dated over a century ago. However, the authors do not explore possible research paths on the subject. It is exactly this gap that we seek to fill in this article by proposing a framework for outlining CB Brazilian scientific futures, which can be applied in different contexts and topics.

Methodology

Our statistical-mathematical instrument is based on the matrix presented by Kayser et. al. (2014), known as portfolio analysis, which provides an overview of emerging and declining keywords. Originally, this tool is composed of the frequency and the relative growth (%) of a keyword in a given time interval. In our model, additionally to absolute frequency (AF) and the relative growth (RG), we added alternative metrics (altmetrics) to the matrix, which consider mentions of academic studies in social networks, such as Twitter and Facebook, citations in blogs and news sites, and in online bibliographic reference management tools, such as Mendeley and CiteULike, allowing to visualise and measure other spheres of influence and impact of scientific production (Priem et al., 2010). Also, considering Mendeley readers as a proxy for future citations, we can identify research trends. Many authors have highlighted the potential of altmetrics for evaluating scientific production in a different and complementary manner than the traditional citation-based indicators (see Spatti et al. 2021).

To set the publications related to CB, we searched for the terms “*Phaseolus vulgaris*”, “common bean”, and “dry bean” in Scopus database (Elsevier) in March, 2021. We add an affiliation filter to identify publications in which at least one of the authors is affiliated to a Brazilian institution and another time frame filter (2010-2019).

Results and Discussion

As per Figure 1, our framework is able to provide an analysis for a given research topic, exemplified in this study by CB. We analysed the frequency of occurrence of keywords, forming a matrix with two axes. The y axis represents the absolute frequency (AF) of the keyword in the total number of papers in the period (2010-2019). The x axis represents the relative growth (RG) (%) of the keyword's frequency in the period 2015-2019, compared to 2010-2014. The size of the bubble represents the indicator that we propose as the Scientific Trend Index (STI) - the arithmetic mean between the sum of the Mendeley readers, Scopus citations and Altmetric Attention score of the publications referring to the keywords.

Figure 1. The matrix for outlining scientific past and futures

Source: own data

Keywords were classified in 4 groups based on the Absolute Frequency and relative growth:

- Core: relevant and established research topics (AF>25; RG>0%)
- Emerging: still not established research topics but with raising relevance in the last period of analysis (AF<25, RG>0%)
- Established: established research topics but little relevant in the last period of analysis (AF>25, RG<0%)
- Declining: not established research topics and little relevant (AF<25, RG<0%)

Brazilian scientific research regarding CB has the keywords “Nitrogen fixation”, “Genotype and Environment Interaction” and “Sclerotinia sclerotiorum” as examples of core research topics. “Plant breeding”, “Yield” and “Anthracnose” are classified as established topics. Examples of emerging topics are “Irrigation”, “Photosynthesis” and “Vigor” and declining topics are “Crop rotation”, “Resistance” and “Phosphorus”.

Conclusion

By mapping varied impact’s dimensions using bibliometrics and altmetrics indicators, our framework is a very good starting point for discussing past and future research, then contributing to identify new research trends and to advance informetric and scientometric theories. We’ve applied it to a topic - Common Beans - which has global relevance and is fundamental to the Brazilian context. By including experts and stakeholders analysis, our framework can enhance the detection and examination of emerging, core, declining and established themes, providing a solid base for discussion and decision making.

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References

- Pritchard, A., (1969). Statistical bibliography or bibliometrics?. *Journal of Documentation*, 24(4), 348-349.
- Keathley-Herring, H., Van Aken, E., Gonzalez-Aleu, F. et al. Assessing the maturity of a research area: bibliometric review and proposed framework. *Scientometrics* 109, 927–951 (2016).
- Yang, C., Huang, C., & Su, J. (2020). A bibliometrics-based research framework for exploring policy evolution: A case study of China's information technology policies. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 157, 120116.
- Y. Zhang, A. L. Porter, S. Cunningham, D. Chiavetta and N. Newman, "Parallel or Intersecting Lines? Intelligent Bibliometrics for Investigating the Involvement of Data Science in Policy Analysis," in *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 1259-1271, Oct. 2021.
- Miano, A. C., Saldaña, E., Campestrini, L. H., Chiorato, A. F., & Augusto, P. E. D. (2018). Correlating the properties of different carioca bean cultivars (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) with their hydration kinetics. *Food Research International*, 107, 182-194.
- Leal, F. T. (2019). Produtividade, qualidade e eficiência de uso do nitrogênio de cultivares de feijoeiro comum.
- Ferreira, C. M. (2021). Movimento “Arroz e Feijão: a comida do Brasil” – proposta para valorização da tradicional alimentação. *Arroz e feijão*, 1.
- Hayat, I., Ahmad, A., Masud, T., Ahmed, A., & Bashir, S. (2014). Nutritional and health perspectives of beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.): an overview. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*, 54(5), 580-592.
- Chiorato, A. F., Reis, L. L. B., Bezerra, L. M. C., & Carbonell, S. A. M. (2018). Global vision on common bean breeding cultivars. *Phaseolus vulgaris: cultivars, production and uses*, 1, 1-41.
- Bezerra, L. M. C., Spatti, A. C., Fredo, C. E., Bin, A., de Carvalho Paulino, J. F., Chiorato, A. F., ... & Correia, G. G. (2022). CC&T. *Cadernos de Ciência & Tecnologia*, 39(1), e26949.
- Spatti, A. C., Cintra, P. R., Bin, A., & Araújo, R. F. Métricas alternativas para avaliação da produção científica latino-americana: um estudo da Rede SciELO. *Informação & Informação*, 26(2), 596-624.
- Kayser, V., Goluchowicz, K., & Bierwisch, A. (2014). Text mining for technology roadmapping-The strategic value of information. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 18(03), 1440004.
- J. Priem, D. Taraborelli, P. Groth, C. Neylon (2010), *Altmetrics: A manifesto*, 26 October 2010. <http://altmetrics.org/manifesto>